

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING AND ITS IMPACT
ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AND PRODUCTIVITY
IN THE TOURISM SECTOR OF GHANA**

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Abstract:

The study aims to explore the impact of Human Resource Development activities on employee performance in Ghana's tourism sector and suggest improvement recommendations. Primary data is collected from staff in different departments, and the multiple correlation-regression analysis is carried out to establish the relationship between five variables including; selection and recruitment, training and development, employee development, training needs assessment, performance appraisal and their effect on employee performance in the tourism sector. The results reveal that the variables have a strong and positive relationship and important in developing training programmes to achieve employee efficiency and building human-capital in the tourism sector.

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1. Introduction

Productivity of Ghana's public sector, in recent times, has become a major concern to the public and scholars alike. There is a clarion call on the public sector, including the tourism sector, to improve on its quality service delivery to ensure productivity and value for money. There are indications that ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs) have poor institutional capacities to formulate and implement policies for improving services provided to the citizenry (NPSRS, 2017). At a national forum, the Senchi National Economic Forum of 2014, the meeting expressed dissatisfaction with the public servant's display of a lackadaisical attitude toward their work. The increasing cases of grievances and the complaints levied against public servants, including those in the tourism sector, has become obvious that there is a skill challenge among officials of basic service delivery being witnessed across the country, including tourism public sector institutions (NPSRS, 2017).

The Public Sector Tourism Administration in Ghana is mandated to design and implement a sector training policy based on the skill gaps identified and needs to improve employee skills and skills at all levels of the tourism sector. The Apex Public Sector Institute, the Ministry of Tourism, Arts and Culture (MOTAC), has always been at the forefront of efforts to constantly address the skill gaps, especially at the management level. The focus of this study is based on the tourism subsector of the tourism, arts and culture industry of Ghana. The tourism and hospitality sector globally is characterised by certain qualities that needed the delivery of tourism and hospitality services by a specific category of workers. One of the main characteristics of the hospitality service is its manufacturing and distribution are therefore inseparable, and this calls for skilled and qualified employees at all levels of the hospitality industry (Lashley, 2002). However, the challenges of service delivery continue to bedevil the tourism sector of Ghana. According to (Hsieh & Chuang, 2019), understanding the key factors affecting service experience is a complex issue for service providers. To address the weak performance in service delivery and improve efficiency and professionalism in public sector institutions, a new direction of purpose; capacity building, and streamlining processes to ensure responsiveness, efficiency in the delivery of service at all levels of governance in the tourism sector (ROG, 2011).

Although studies on Public Service Performance and its impact on ensuring efficiency and effectiveness of public service delivery in Ghana have been conducted, there is limited previous scholarly work on the effectiveness of HRD practice in the tourism sector and its impact on employee performance and productivity. This presents a gap in literature that needs to be interrogated. Researchers have become increasingly

aware of the gaps between the findings of research and management practice (Rynes et al. 2002a, b). Two distinct gaps were acknowledged. Firstly, practitioners cannot implement what they are not familiar with, and this creates a 'knowing' gap. Secondly, practitioners may know and fail to implement research findings. Previous studies examined the definition of HRD practices and their relationship with the organisation and concluded that HRD practices vary as they are influenced by different factors from one organisation and country to another. These factors could be internal (e.g., organisational size, organisational structure, business strategy, organisational culture) or external factors (economic, technological change, industry characteristics, national culture, legalisation and regulations, competitors and globalisation), according to (Bloom & Van Reenen, 2010).

To achieve the overall objective of the study, the following objectives will be examined: to analyse the impact of HRD practice on employee performance in the tourism sector; to explore the relationship between HRD practice and tourism productivity; to provide meaningful analysis of HRD practices on how it affects quality service delivery in the tourism sector.

2. Significance and Purpose of the Research

This study would significantly broaden the knowledge boundary and current academic literacy on the effectiveness of training in the tourism industry of Ghana through an empirical analysis. This will interrogate the relationship between HRD activities including; selection and recruitment, training and development, employee development, training needs assessment, performance appraisal and how these impact the productivity levels in the tourism sector of Ghana. The purpose of this study is to address the challenge of inadequate skilled labour in the sector that continues to hinder quality service delivery in the tourism and hospitality industry (ROG, 2011) and explore the impact of HRD activities on employee performance and productivity of the tourism sector and to propose recommendations for improvement.

2.1 Theoretical Framework of the Study

Although several different theoretical positions can explain the understanding of the effectiveness of training and its impact on employee performance and productivity in the tourism industry of Ghana. The Human Capital Theory is an important theory under which the arguments of this study are grounded.

The fast growth and the application of information and communication technology has become a necessity for human capital development in the tourism industry. Human capital is a mixture of Knowledge, skills, and experiences that individuals acquire overtime. Human capital determines the amount of economic development and scientific-technical advancement under modern socio-economic circumstances.

2.1.1 Human Capital Theory and Tourism Development

The tourism industry plays a major role in many countries' economic development (Ogarlaci, 2012). In the challenging job of offering excellent customer service to clients whose expectations are high by the increase in knowledge and technology, the sector is witnessing powerful internal competition between actors and managers. The lack of training programmes, which concentrate on tourism, hospitality and leisure, for practitioners in the industry are a significant task that must be addressed (Popescu et al., 2013). The result is an adverse effect on the perception of the industry, corporate productivity, and financial performance. Consequently, the industry's potential contribution to economic growth and poverty alleviation remains untapped in developed economies. Therefore, it is essential to invest in human capital to guide the growth of the country's tourism industry.

The fact that the tourism industry is linked to tourism and hospitality services, contributes to the need to hire, recruit and invest in human resources. This highlights the need for a competent and flexible workforce to compete in the 21st century. Investing in human resources through multiple courses is achieved by investment in education, through different courses, and training programs. From the classical economics perspective, human capital considers labour as a purchase and sale commodity (Marimuthu et al., 2009). Also, they explain that the knowledge, know-how, and skill that one acquires through education and training is the human capital.

Becker (1993), said that investment in human beings is the most valuable of all capital. Becker draws a dichotomy between firm-specific human capital from human capital for general purposes, which explains that firm-specific human capital includes knowledge gained through training in hospitality management and marketing, accounting procedures, and management of information, or other firm/industry-specific expertise in particular. These features improve the well-being or add to a person's literary debt over a lifetime of creating wealth. Human capital for the general purpose is knowledge gained by educating and training in value areas for a range of firms, such as generic skills in the development of human resources. Becker affirms that education and training are the most essential human capital investment. Figure 1 presents the key links and assumptions underlying the Human Capital Theory.

Figure 1: A Model of Human Capital Theory (Swanson, 2001)
 (Source: A Model of Human Capital Theory (Swanson, 2001: 110))

Relationship 1: postulates a production function concept as applied to education and training. The hypothesis of this relationship is that development in tourism and hospitality education and training results in increased learning and delivery of quality service.

Relationship 2: postulates the human capital relationship between education and increased employee performance and productivity. The theory behind this relationship is that there is a positive impact on productivity in the hospitality industry through improved training and quality service delivery.

Relationship 3: postulates the human capital relationship between increased employee performance and productivity and higher wages and income. The underlying theory is that improved employee performance and productivity in the hospitality sector leads to higher employee wages and increased profit for the sector. In summary, human capital contributes to the competitiveness of any organisation, including the tourism and hospitality industry, hence its application in this study.

3. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

The conceptual framework underpinning this study is a multi-dimensional approach developed from the prepositions of HRD activities and how they impact employee performance and productivity in the tourism industry as shown in figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework of the Study
 (Source: Authors' conceptual framework (2019))

The complete participation of the employees of an organisation in the service delivery process makes tourism services much more specific; employees directly engaged in the provision of services, thus affecting the quality of tourism services and the satisfaction of customers. The human factor is a major factor in tourism service quality volatility and uniqueness. People with certain expertise, abilities, and experience are a tourist enterprise's primary value and productive force. Investments in higher education and training in personal training and growth are therefore of outstanding importance. The tourist offer's quality and competitiveness depend directly on these investments.

4. Tourism Development and Employee Performance in Ghana

Like any service sector, tourism depends heavily on labour with a broad informal industry. It has the potential to create jobs and income for the poor, women, young people and disabled people who are often finding it difficult to find jobs in the formal sector (Sonne J., 2010). Available statistics from the World Travel and Tourism Council, (WTTC 2017), show that in 2016, travel and tourism generated US\$7.6 trillion (10.2% of global GDP) and 292 million jobs. The WTTC further projects that the tourism sector could support over 380 million jobs by 2027 and also predicted growth rates of between 5% and 6% per annum for Africa and South Asia. In the works of (Frechtling, 2010), (Kvartalnov, 2003), (Ilic and Nikolic, 2018), the positive impact of tourism on the country's economy is reflected. Tourism plays an exceptional role in building GDP, providing employment, and triggering foreign trade balance in many countries, according to (Pirozhenko, 2012). In Ghana, direct and indirect employment in the tourism industry increased from 172,838 in 2005 to 324,000 in 2011, according to the

Ghana Tourism Authority (GTA) (ROG, 2012). According to the 15-years tourism development plan, Ghana is anticipating an increase inflows of tourist from 746,500 in 2010 to 4,320,000 in 2027 with resultant earnings of USD 1.5 billion in 2010 to 8.5 billion in 2027 while generating about 1.4 million direct and indirect jobs by 2027 (ROG, 2012). The projections are conservative estimates that will depend primarily on tourism authorities' policy stance to improve infrastructure requirements, quality service delivery, and intensive tourism promotion in Ghana.

The projections in the industry can only be attained and maintained with the needed human resource. A casual study of human resource efficiency in the tourism industry since 1996 indicates some progress but, due to minimal or lack of relevant data, it is very difficult to quantify (ROG, 2012). There is, however, a shortage in the supply of qualified, trained, and efficient personnel to deliver quality service, thus posing serious challenges to the future development and competitiveness of the industry (ROG, 2011). Although education and training was provided in Ghana to both public and private employees, it was not done efficiently and systematically (ROG, 2012). However, it is not easy to find evidence for such practices. This raises the challenge of successful decision-making that the industry faces with data collection and processing. The potential quantity of human resources of Ghana in the tourism industry is exceptional, but it is necessary to develop the requisite professional and technical skills to effectively perform their assigned tasks (ROG, 2012). There is, therefore, a substantial difference between the quality and quantity of the human resources needs of the tourism industry (ROG, 2011). Therefore, it is important to ensure that the human resources capital of Ghana's tourism industry is given the necessary training to provide highly qualified professionals who meet the demands and supply needs of the industry, provide quality services to tourism, improve productivity in support of the conceptual framework of the study as presented in Fig. 1.

5. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

5.1 Recruitment, Selection and Employee Performance in the Tourism Industry

In all tourism and hospitality organisations, recruitment and selection of individuals to fill new or existing positions is a key component to human resources activity, whatever its size, structure or activity. The significance of delivering quality service has increased the pressure on organisations to select the 'right' type of person, it is often suggested that choices are made in an informal, ad hoc and reactive way too often. Employers in the UK and elsewhere in hospitality and tourism are increasingly finding the 'right' attitude and staff appearance (Chan and Coleman, 2004; Nickson et al., 2005). What is essential, however, is to ensure that the staffs are engaged in the realisation of organisational objectives rather than getting the precise individuals in the right location at the right moment.

To select the best possible candidate for the position available, the employer or organisation must build a large pool of applicants to choose the best candidate for the

optimal approach throughout the selection process. Indeed, in considering why it may be hard for tourism and hospitality businesses to pursue the best practices in recruitment and choice, (Lockyer & Scholarios, 2005) acknowledge that the absence of formality can often be overcome by using local networks effectively to recruit staff. They recommend, for example, the person responsible for the selection should be able to use informal networks to find suitable workers and have excellent local knowledge of the labour market. Another point that should be regarded is the idea of "fit" between the person and organisation who seek to attract and acknowledge the people who are deemed to be "right" for the organisation, in matters such as engagement, flexibility, quality, teamwork capacity and so on. The interaction between the person and the organisation can, therefore, be "loose," which means that candidates can do the work or "stretched," if the person must prove not only technical skills, but whether the person has a particular personality profile to "fit" in the organisational culture. Therefore, the organisation's efficient and active processes of recruitment and selection lead to a better quality of employees.

H1: Selection and recruitment of tourism staff are positively related to employee performance in the tourism industry.

5.2 Effective HRD in Tourism (Training and Development)

The characteristics of tourism highlight, several features that significantly affect individuals in this industry and the role that human resource development (HRD) plays in promoting increased productivity and quality service at all levels of the industry. HRD is a significant problem facing the global tourism and hospitality sector (Baum, 2002, 2006, 2007a 2008; Boxall and Purcell, 2008; Nickson, 2007). While the obstacles to HRD in the developed world are important, they are restricted by the wider difficulties faced by developing countries, which often have restricted and low equipment, resource and traditional training (Baum, 2008; Hai-yan & Baum, 2006; Kaplan, 2004). The tourism industry cannot grow and become a significant financial driver without HRD. If service standards are low and tourist experience is affected by staff training, this will have a direct impact on the benefits of tourist trade as well as the resulting profits and job creation.

5.2.1 Effective Tourism Training and Human Resource Development

Training is an effort to transfer skills and knowledge to trainees so that they accept and use the skills in their jobs (Kelly, 1998). Training and development is recommended as a key business practice to ensure that tourism employees feel respected, to help reduce staff turnover and to ensure that employees promoted to supervisory or managerial positions can perform effectively (Cho & Kang, 2005). The tourism and hospitality industry is service-oriented and rely on their staff to provide their clients with quality service experiences (Kandampully & Kandampully, 2006). For any organisation, however, the tourism industry in particular, adequate and relevant training is necessary to achieve its goals and objectives in this competitive world. Training is necessary to

enhance the skills, the faculty of reasoning and the skills (Lynton & Pareek, 2000), which can improve corporate performance (Bowen & Ostroff, 2004) and also improve competitiveness (Breiter & Hoart, 2000) in the tourism industry alike.

The majority of previous studies show that the relationship between human resources management and corporate performance is strongly positive (Purcell et al. 2003). According to (WTTC, 1997), education and training programmes in tourism have a positive effect on workers' know-how, skills and capacity as one of the most important practices in the management of human resources, leading to a higher work performance. The transition from training to development represents an increasing understanding of human resources' strategic implications. Employee development serves two objectives: organisational efficiency improvement and employee development. Learning is essential in both cases. More specifically, the basis on which organisational achievement and individual growth are realised is learning capacity. Development is employee performance through scheduled and structured procedures at all management levels.

The primary objective of employee development is to make the best possible use of the ability of staff. Therefore, the development of staff is an organised activity of the professional growth of staff (Laing & Andrew, 2011). Potential advantages should be evident for training programs addressing particular issues or possibly rewarding possibilities. However, the advantages are usually less evident for less particular instruction with vague intent. Essentially, any training's payoff will be to boost profit or cut expenses.

The effectiveness of the tourism sector of Ghana largely depends on the ability to ensure effective and efficient use of the human resource because it is a strategic resource to achieve the sector's objectives to realise its total ability to contribute to economic wealth, poverty alleviation, protection of the environment, national cohesion and achieve greater gross domestic product (GDP). This suggests that there is a direct relationship in the planning and implementation of effective training to ensuring efficiency in employee development and performance.

H2: Effective Tourism training and development is positively related to employee performance in the tourism industry.

H3: Employee development in the tourism sector is positively related to employee performance in the tourism industry.

5.3 Tourism Training Needs Analysis

The tourism and hospitality industry is characterised by certain qualities that required a specialised category of staff in the delivery of tourism and hospitality services. One of the major features of hospitality service, according to (Susskind, A. M. et al., 2000), is that its production and delivery are inseparable, which calls skillful and competent staff at all levels of the hospitality industry. According to (Brown, 2002), training needs analysis / trained need assessment is intended to identify the needs or performance

requirements of an organisation to help the most needful, organisational targets, enhance productivity and deliver products and services of quality resources.

Kaplan (2004) examines the role of skill development in the tourism-led development strategy of South Africa and finds that lack of an organised and structured approach to the development of tourism skills restricts the contribution of skill development to the transformation of tourism. In managing a large number of unskilled and low-skilled workers in the tourism and hospitality industry, finding the right kind of training that fits business needs and trainees can be difficult (Teng, 2008). The major challenge facing tourism and hospitality industries is adapting their skill requirements to the ever-changing labour market in both developed and underdeveloped countries

To assess whether training has been successful or not, it is necessary to evaluate the results. Training programme evaluation enhances the quality of training, selects efficient programmes and rejects inefficient programmes (Kuchеров & Manokhina, 2017). Therefore, after the training programme evaluation should consider which tools will determine the effectiveness of the delivered programmes. Evaluation determines the relevance, effectiveness, and impact of activities taking into account their goals (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006). The above-mentioned TNA concepts have all helped the development of the TNA process in various ways. However, there is some understanding as to how to make the TNA comprehensive and effective in achieving the desired results through employee development. TNA as a basic HRD activity from the review of previous studies has a strong relation to employee development. As a result, the enhancement of the employee's quality in the tourism sector is influenced by a comprehensive TNA.

H4: Training needs assessment in the tourism sector positively impacts an employee's performance in the tourism industry

5.4 Performance Management and Productivity in the Tourism Industry

Performance management is a continuous process in which individuals and teams identify, measure and develop performance and align their performance with their strategic goals. In particular, performance management is about aligning individual goals with organisational goals and ensuring that individuals maintain corporate core values. Appraisal of performance, which is a critical element of performance management and a main feature of organisational life, is one of the most significant elements of performance enhancement. As (Bach, 2005: 289) states, performance assessments have become much more than just an annual ritual and are seen as the main lever for improving organisational performance.

5.4.1 Performance appraisal management in tourism management

Heery and Noon (2001: 7) define performance assessment as the process of assessing performance and assessing an employee's development/training requirements. Performance appraisal is considered an important and integral part of performance management and a basic tool for communication and understanding between

employer-employee in workplaces of all types (Aguinis, 2013; Pulakos et al., 2012). The primary objective of a performance appraisal is to ensure the maximisation of every employee's skills, knowledge, and interests (ICAI 2014). Previous research investigated the impact of individual and organisational outcomes of performance appraisal. Danvers & Keeling (1995) argued that performance appraisal could benefit from several functions, such as assistance in employee training and remuneration. However, managers are in doubt that performance appraisal can accomplish many tasks, such as providing feedback, training and skills growth, and the ability to use information and knowledge (Kor & Sundaramurthy, 2009). Another study by (Soomro et al., 2011) concluded that the activities of the HRD are positively correlated with the quality of employees.

Employers depend on performance appraisal to determine whether organisational goals are being achieved and customer satisfaction sustained. Conversely, employees also get feedback on it for reassurance of satisfactory work and the guarantee for continued employment. The employee-employer both rely on it for intuition into employee motivation, satisfaction, and engagement, all of which are linked to employee performance and productivity in the tourism sector.

H5: Performance appraisal of tourism staff is positively related to employee performance in the tourism industry

6. Methods and Materials

The study interrogates the linear relationship between HRD activities and how these impact employee performance and productivity levels in the tourism sector of Ghana. This is premised on a theoretical research foundation, the Human Capital Theory by (Swanson 2001), as presented in figure 1 showing three relationships: education and training results in increased learning; increased learning does impact productivity positively; improved productivity result in higher wages for individuals and enhanced profit for businesses. Considering the objective of the study a quantitative approach was employed to source primary data through the use of standard questionnaires by interviewing employees of the public sector institutions administering the tourism industry in Ghana.

The random probability sampling technique was used to collect primary data from respondents using standard questionnaires with tested validity and reliability. Accordingly, 98 respondents out of 120 selected participated with a margin of 0.05 error (95% confidence level) taken for a population of about 450 staff from different departments including HRD, Policy Planning, Quality Assurance, Research and Statistics, Finance and Administration, Regional staff, and occupied various positions ranging from middle management to Managerial positions. The sample size of this study is determined according to the table of (Bartlet et al., 2001), and the Kaiser / Meyer / Olkin (KMO) test was applied to determine the sample adequacy for the study.

To ensure the reliability of the research, the Cronbach's alpha was applied to determine if the data collection instrument is designed to collate the required variable or not. The HRD activities were analysed employing 33 items consisted of 5 independent variables including; selection and recruitment, training and development, employee development, training needs assessment, performance appraisal; likewise, the dependent variable employee performance

The Primary data collected were analysed using the SPSS version 22 to process the descriptive statistics. The multiple correlation-regression model was used to analyse the data to establish the relationship between five variables of human resource development activities such as training, training needs assessment, employee development and performance and their impact on employee performance and productivity in the tourism sector of Ghana.

7. Discussion and Findings

Standard questionnaires with tested validity and reliability were prepared and distributed to the sampled employees of the tourism industry to assess their perception regarding the practices of HRD activities and the productivity of the tourism sector. In all, 120 questionnaires were distributed and 98 (81.67%) sampled employees filled the questionnaires properly and return them on time and the remaining 22 (18.33%) questionnaires were not returned. The margin of 0.05 error (95% confidence level) was applied for a population under study according to the table of (Bartlet et al., 2001).

7.1 Demography of Respondents

The descriptive analysis revealed that out of the total respondents of the questionnaire, 37 (37.75%) were females and 61 (62.25%) were males. The ages of the majority of respondents were below 40 years (76.1 %). Regarding the educational status of the respondents, most of the sample (56.8 %) are first-degree holders, 29.3% have a college diploma, and only 14.2% are second-degree holders. Concerning respondents' service years in the tourism sector, 48.5% of the samples (48) have been working in the sector for less than five years, 33.4% of them (33) have worked between 5 and 10 years work experience in the sector and only the rest 17.1% (17) were working for more than ten years. This indicates a little over half of the sample (50) have more than 5 years' experience in the tourism sector and the other 48 have less than 5 years of experience.

7.2 Reliability and Validity Analysis of Survey Instruments

The motivation behind this study is to examine the relationship that exists among the HRD activities and its impact on employee performance and productivity in the tourism sector of Ghana. To ensure the reliability of the study, the Cronbach's alpha is tested to determine the reliability of the variables as presented in table 1. below. The result shows an overall reliability ($\alpha \leq 0.82$), indicative of the reliability and validity of the variables as applied in the study.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis of Variables

Variables	Questions/items	Alpha value
Selection and Recruitment	5	0.83
Training and Development	8	0.91
Employee Development	6	0.85
Training Needs Assessment	4	0.77
Performance Appraisal	5	0.74
Employee Performance	5	0.89
Overall	33	0.80

The HRD activities is measured by 33 items consisted of 5 independent variables likewise, the dependent variable employee performance. A 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from -2 to 2 where -2 means very dissatisfied and 2 means very satisfied to elicit primary data for the alpha score of the Cronbach (reliability statistics). Cronbach's coefficient (α) is used to calculate the reliability of survey measurement instruments, for example, questionnaires, and findings are presented in Table 1, In terms of their individual and accumulated values, each variable indicates that the given items are correct and reliable. The overall score was 0.80, which represents excellent reliability. The alpha of the Cronbach varies from 0 to 1 and 0 for absolutely unreliable and 1 for a fully reliable sample.

The Kaiser / Meyer / Olkin (KMO) test and the Bartlett sphericity test were used to determine the appropriateness of the 28 items applied in the study. The KMO test ensured overall sampling adequacy estimation, which was 0.901 (> 0.50), and Bartlett's test endorsed the appropriateness of the items, which was 1505.317, $df= 215$, significant at $p < 0.01$. The results from the principal component analysis revealed that, 28 out of the 39 items were significantly related and could be placed into 5 appropriate categories to undertake the study.

8. Analysis and Results

Table 2 presents the multiple regression analysis and found that five factors of HRD activities (i.e., selection and recruitment, training and development, employee development, training needs assessment, performance appraisal) together significantly predict employee performance. The relationship between variables is significant from the correlation regression analysis at 0.05 levels, whereas, in Table 3, the level of significance F-statistics ($28.041 = 28.0$, $P < 0.05$ and $\pm 5\%$ margin of error with an $R^2 = 0.462$) means nearly 46 percent of employee performance is explained collectively by all HRD activities.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis and how the Variables are Related

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Selection and Recruitment	1					
2. Training and Development	0.246**	1				
3. Employee Development	0.507**	0.401**	1			
4. Training needs Assessment	0.591**	0.318**	0.437**	1		
5. Performance Appraisal	0.625**	0.253**	0.352**	0.464**	1	
6. Employee Performance	0.503**	0.262**	0.298**	0.307**	0.351**	1

*Indicate significance at 10%, ** Indicate significance at 5% and, *** Indicate significance at 1%

Table 3 also presents a positive relationship between the variables at the level of significance F-statistics (28.041) = 28.0, $P < 0.05$. The regression analysis also re-affirms the results of the correlation analysis establishing a positive relationship among the HRD activities understudy in the tourism industry in Ghana.

Table 3: ANOVA

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	13.209	6	6.389	28.041	0.000
Residual	19.697	115	0.18		
Total	32.906	121			

Dependent variable: Employee Performance. Predictors: (Constant) Selection and Recruitment, Training and Development, Employee Development, Training needs Assessment, Performance Appraisal.

Table 4: Regression Analysis with R²

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error
	0.680 ^a	0.462	0.447	0.43573

Predictors: (Constant) Selection and Recruitment, Training and Development, Employee Development, Training needs Assessment, Performance Appraisal.

At an estimation of (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.446$) meaning, about 45% of the employees' productive performance is explained by all the HRD activities. The findings of this study illustrate that the HRD activities (selection and recruitment, training and development, employee development, training needs assessment, performance appraisal) positively impact employees' productivity and eventually the success or the delivery of quality tourism services. Findings of previous studies support this argument: the Human Capital Theory by (Swanson 2001) postulates that increased learning impacts positively on employee performance and productivity. Therefore, the tourism sector should endeavour to attract and retain the best skills, well trained and enthusiastic employees and committed to their work. This will mean designing and implementing HRD policies that can transform the sector to create wealth in our local communities supporting the conceptual framework of the study. Training according to (DeCenzo & Robbins, 2005) can be costly, and should not be considered a cure-all of the organisation's ailments. Rather, judge training by its contribution to performance, where performance depends on motivation, skills, and abilities to succeed.

Table 5 below presents the analysis of the summary of the hypothesis of the study. The correlated result of the hypotheses of the study is significant at the 0.05 level, indicating a strong relationship among the hypotheses, validating the reliability of the findings of this study.

Table 5: A Summary of Hypothesis Analysis

Hypothesis	Correlation	Result
H1: Selection and recruitment of tourism staff are positively related to employee performance in the tourism industry	0.514**	Supported
H2: Effective Tourism training is positively related to employee performance in the tourism industry	0.525**	Supported
H3: Employee development in the tourism sector is positively related to employee performance in the tourism industry	0.387**	Supported
H4: Training needs assessment in the tourism sector positively impacts an employee's performance in the tourism industry	0.294**	Supported
H5: Performance appraisal of tourism staff is positively related impacts an employee's performance in the tourism industry	0.621**	Supported

9. Conclusion and Recommendation

9.1 Conclusion

The study explored the impact of HRD activities on employee performance and productivity in the tourism sector of Ghana and make recommendations for its improvement to achieve high-quality service delivery to position Ghana as a preferred tourist destination in the West African Sub-region. The findings of this study illustrate that the HRD activities (selection and recruitment, training and development, employee development, training needs assessment, performance appraisal) are significantly related and impact the Ministry of Tourism Arts and Cultures' productivity positively. It, therefore, behooves management to pay much attention to the HRD activities of the sector and implement HR policies that can drive the sector into professionalism. According to the Human Capital Theory, the theoretical framework applied in this study, the HRD activities are essential agents for stimulating growth in the tourism sector, and this will to create jobs and wealth in our local economy to alleviate poverty.

It is important to continuously improve the knowledge base of the employees of the tourism sector to deliver quality service to attract the attention of its clients. Training also improves the wellbeing or add to a person's indebtedness of literature over a lifetime upon which wealth is created. From a classical theory of Economics, human capital considers labour as a product that could be sold (Marimuthu et al. 2009). The role of the employees in improving Ghana's tourism sector globally is significant and strategic. Training based on specific needs and objectives should, therefore, be developed to increase the productivity of the tourism sector, stimulate employees' performance and skills. The sector should consider training as an investment that contributes not only to a high return but also promotes competitive advantages to position Ghana as a tourists' destination of choice within the West African Sub-region.

9.2 Recommendation

To expand Ghana's tourism sector to improve job creation and prospecting, the service culture in Ghana must be improved and exceed customer expectations. An assessment and review should be performed for all existing staff, to determine the differences in job descriptions and job requirements. This will help develop appropriate training and development programmes for existing employees and identify new employment opportunities. The exercise should include potential hiring processes and selection of workers for MOTAC and GTA. The principal goal is to increase the performance of employees so that new and existing employees can perform their jobs efficiently by developing a holistic recruitment and training policy for the tourism sector. The training policy must focus on:

- 1) Ensuring establishing an effective TNA as supported in the literature review of the study to include; data collection and collation on staff training, analysis of training feedbacks and planning for appropriate training for employees. To efficiently do this, management should ensure that staff are consulted and their training needs properly addressed. This also enhances pre-training motivation and the design of training programmes, which are essential for employee development. An effective TNA also influence management decision on the caliber of new staff to be recruited. Furthermore, previous research has established that individual employees may differ from each other in terms of their ability to perform their duties, which is why it is justified to conduct continuous TNA to examine the effect of 'best practices' of HRD activities on the performance of employees, especially in the tourism industry where the provision and consumption of tourism services occur at the same time.
- 2) Management of the tourism sector can also rely on performance assessment to determine the training needs and compensation for employees Performance. Appraisals also provide a win-win situation for both employee-employer since both rely on it for intuition into employee motivation, satisfaction, and engagement, all of which are linked to employee productivity in the tourism sector. Employees further receive comments to reassure them that their work is satisfactory and that they can be guaranteed continued work through the appraisal system.

9.3 Implications for Future Research and Limitations

To improve the productivity and competitiveness of the tourism sector, it behooves management of the tourism sector to implement HRD activities (selection and recruitment, training and development, employee development, training needs assessment, performance appraisal). Future studies should consider extending the sample to include the private sector tourism and hospitality service providers (hotels, tour operators restaurants, entertainment centres among others). The outcome of such a study is very useful for generalising the findings.

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